

Experimental Assessment of Positioning Precision During Free-hand and Robot-assisted Tool Manipulation in Transoral Microsurgery Model

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Abstract—Transoral laser microsurgery (TLM) is a vocal cord cancer treatment where surgical tools reach the targeted region through the mouth. A robot-assisted system could aid in such operation yet there is limited understanding of the precision that is reachable at the level of the vocal folds. Therefore, this paper analyzed the baseline of human tool positioning capability during simulated TLM. In a simulated TLM environment, 31 participants navigated a probe to reach the target region of variable diameter ranging from 2.0 mm to 0.1 mm. The total execution time and the number of incorrect contacts were recorded. To assess the positioning potential under robotic assistance, 5 volunteers conducted the same tasks with the help of a co-manipulation robot. The minimum target diameter humans can precisely achieve at the vocal fold is 1.5 mm (time: mean = 13.92 s, SD = 12.30 s, incorrect contact: mean = 2.71, SD = 4.53) while with the co-manipulation system, the precision can be improved to 0.2 mm (time: mean = 21.20 s, SD = 12.31 s, incorrect contact: mean = 3.84, SD = 2.95). The experiments successfully established a baseline for free-hand precision reachable at the vocal fold and potential improvement through robot assistance.

Index Terms—Minimally invasive surgery, Transoral laser microsurgery, Vocal fold, Human precision, Positioning precision, Robot assistance, Co-manipulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

MINIMALLY Invasive Surgery (MIS) is an increasingly popular surgical technique in head and neck surgery because it helps minimize tissue damage, reduces trauma, shortens recovery time, and increases the patient's quality of life. One of the main challenges in head and neck surgery is the treatment of the vocal fold as it is the deepest part of the larynx where accessibility, visualization, and tool manipulation are difficult. Approximately 300,000 patients suffer from vocal fold cancer annually which can lead to voice loss or death if not treated [1]. Transoral Laser Microsurgery (TLM) is a clinical approach to treat vocal fold cancer. In TLM, tools are inserted through the mouth to operate within the confined space of the larynx [2]. Surgeons need to perform delicate tissue manipulations using long and slender tools with one hand while viewing the targeting area through a surgical microscope. Surgeons control the laser system with their other hand to ablate and dissect the tissue [2].

A method of using a robotic system to perform transoral surgery is called Transoral Robotic Surgery (TORS). TORS

Fig. 1: Simulated TLM experimental setup. A target pattern (shown in Fig. 2) is inserted into a mock-up laryngoscope and located at the same position as the patient's vocal folds in TLM. Participants navigate the probe to the target pattern by visualizing through the binocular lens of the microscope. The processor unit recorded all data regarding the probe states.

was reported to offer improved visualization and better tool manipulation at the surgical target [3]–[5]. So far, notable state-of-the-art commercial robot-assisted systems for transoral surgery are the da Vinci Xi and single port (SP) version (Intuitive Surgical, Sunnyvale, CA), and the Flex[®] robotic system (Medrobotics Corp., Raynham, MA) [6].

Some studies on TORS with da Vinci and Flex[®] reported promising outcomes [4], [7]–[11], but several limitations are still prevalent. A prominent issue is the difficulty of reaching the deeper part of the larynx where the vocal folds reside. In particular, the overall size of all the da Vinci versions and the Flex[®] robotic system is too large to conveniently reach the vocal folds [4], [5]. Aside from the size constraint, while Flex[®]'s design is more dedicated toward TORS, depth perception remains troublesome. [5], [11]. Additionally, these commercial robotic systems require dedicated instruments rather than allowing the use of conventional TLM instruments. Due to this factor, the cost of one intervention of the current commercial robotic system is high and not feasible as a standard solution [6].

Novel robot-assisted devices are being developed to alleviate these challenges. Notable developments include the CALM system developed by the Italian Institute of Technology under the European Union collaboration μ RALP project [12], [13]. CALM is a teleoperated robot-assisted system for TLM where the laser can be controlled with a stylus on a tablet. In tandem with laser control, surgeons can view the surgical site through a live camera as an alternative to viewing through a microscope, granting improved accuracy and controllability. Another research prototype is the ACTORS system developed by the National University of Singapore. ACTORS is a transoral surgery robot with a rod-based parallel mechanism composed of superelastic nickel-titanium material to improve flexibility while maintaining benefits from rigid links [14]. Similar to commercial robot systems, the miniaturization of the novel robot-assisted system remained a challenge to effectively reach the vocal fold.

A few tasks during TLM still require manual tool manipulation. Also, these tasks could benefit from an assistive system. This study first tries to establish the governing positioning precision achieved during manual operation as a baseline to set meaningful design requirements for a dedicated robot to assist with tool manipulation and for further optimizing laser control. At the validation state of robot-assisted system development, the simulated TLM test setup could be used to compare the performance of free-hand manipulation with the robot-assisted system.

Currently, there are a number of works that analyze the precision of free-hand motion [15]–[19]. However, these works mostly focus on the tremor effect rather than on pinpointing accuracy and precision. The performance also depends on the specific surgical intervention that each study is designed for. For example, Gijbels *et al.* [15] and Mitchell *et al.* [20] analyze tremors and performance of an assistive system for vitreoretinal surgery, Siyar *et al.* [17] analyze tremors in neurosurgery, and Coulson *et al.* [18] designed a general experiment to assess hand tremor in microsurgery. To the authors' knowledge, no study evaluates the human tool positioning capability for TLM at the level of the vocal folds.

The main contribution of this study is the development of a test mockup to gather data on tool positioning precision in the TLM environment. This setup is used to assess human positioning precision where the results aim to establish a baseline for human precision in such an environment. In addition, the same experiment is performed with a related robot-assisted system, designed for another medical application but with relevant degrees of freedom, to observe how effective such a system could potentially improve positioning performance.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows: section II explains the simulated TLM experiment setup and equipment, section III discusses the experimental procedure, section IV presents the results, section V discusses the major findings, and section VI concludes the article.

II. EXPERIMENT SETUP IN TLM ENVIRONMENT

During a standard transoral laser surgery procedure in the larynx, the patient is put on a bed in a supine posture. He/she

Fig. 2: The laryngoscope model used in the experiment. The top section shows the two interchangeable photolithography disks with circular target patterns. The disk is made with p-type silicon semiconductor (white circular region) with a platinum coating (shaded region). The circular target size ranged from 2.0 mm down to 0.1 mm. The bottom section shows the custom-made probe with similar dimensions to tools used in TLM. The tip is bent 15 degrees to one side of its longitudinal axis to avoid its shaft from blocking the view when observing the probe tip through the microscope.

is then anesthetized and a laryngoscope is inserted into the throat. The laryngoscope acts as a rigid passage for tools to operate on the targeted area, effectively shielding the larynx from collision with instruments [2]. The targeted area in this case is a region at the vocal fold level beyond the distal end of the laryngoscope. This is a circular area of approximately 12 mm diameter according to the study of human larynx anatomy by Eckel *et al.* [21]. Surgeons then insert a long and slender surgical tool through an 18-centimeter-long laryngoscope to operate on the target site.

A setup was built to simulate relevant motions that the tissue manipulation instruments represent during vocal fold surgery. Sensors were integrated into the setup to allow measuring the positioning precision. Figure 1 shows the mock-up laryngoscope setup that was developed. The laryngoscope is 3D-printed to have the same tubular section dimension as the surgical laryngoscope used in TLM. The setup is positioned in the operating room where the actual surgical microscope for TLM was used during these experiments. Participants visualize the surgical site (the target pattern) through the binocular lens of this microscope as they normally would in TLM. The video recording function of the microscope is being used during the experiment to record the tool motion at the target site. A view from such recordings is shown in Fig. 1. Right next to the patient bed is an external screen displaying the microscope's vision for the experiment responsible to monitor, and a PC

to record signals from the processor unit. A custom-made photolithography pattern of circular-shaped target points with variable diameters was slid in the mock-up laryngoscope as shown in Fig. 2. The two disks in Fig. 2 could easily be switched during the experiment by sliding in and out from the casing of the laryngoscope. The photolithography disk is positioned at the level of the vocal folds. Each circular target in the disk (indicated with the number 1 to 7 in Fig. 2) represents a simulated target with a different difficulty level that the participant needs to reach during the experiment. A custom-made probe is used to simulate the surgical tool. More details for each component are explained in the following subsection.

A. Probe

A custom-made conductive stainless steel probe with a length of 300 mm and a diameter of 1.7 mm is used to mimic the length and shape of conventional tools used in TLM (Fig. 2). The probe tip is tapered and bent over 15 degrees over a length of 1 cm from the longitudinal axis similar to a few instruments used in TLM. This is to avoid blocking the view when observing the probe tip through the surgical microscope. TLM has different instruments with varying tip bending angles. The 15-degree angle is chosen to optimize the visual through the microscope during this experiment. The needle tip has a diameter of 40 microns, ensuring that the contact point is smaller than the smallest target of 0.1 mm. The deformation of the probe is not considered as there is no external load during its navigation path. The deformation due to its own weight when navigating is not visible and thus contributes less effect on the precision compared to the tremor effect from the length of the probe.

B. Photolithography pattern

A convenient way to estimate positioning precision as introduced by Gijbels *et al.* [15] consists of producing a structure with variable resistance and asking the operator to contact a region with a specific resistance. Photolithography is a photo-etching technology that precisely coats one material onto another with a resolution in the order of nanometers [22]. The aforementioned pattern is made by a photolithography method using a p-type silicon semiconductor wafer as a base with a platinum coating. The size of these circular patterns are, as shown in Fig. 2, 2.0 mm, 1.5 mm, 1.0 mm, 0.8 mm, 0.4 mm, 0.2 mm, and 0.1 mm respectively. The detection of analog electrical signals (voltage) is the method to determine the probe state. A voltage divider circuit is constructed as shown in Fig. 3 to determine the position of the probe. The grey-shaded regions, terminal 1 (T_1) and terminal 2 (T_2), have a platinum coating. The white circular pattern is the p-type silicon semiconductor that only starts conducting electricity when a voltage is applied. Terminal 3 (T_3) is a conductive long and slender probe used in this experiment. T_1 and T_2 are completely separated by the p-type silicon (notice the vertical line that goes through each circular pattern in Fig. 3). R_c is the constant resistance connected to a 5V input voltage +V. R_1 and R_2 are the variable resistance of the p-type silicon semiconductor along the path T_1 - T_3 and T_2 - T_3 respectively.

Fig. 3: Voltage divider circuit to determine the probe state during the experiment. The four possible probe states are “on T_2 ”, “on target”, “on T_1 ”, and “disconnected”.

This circuit enables distinction between four different probe states namely: on T_1 , on T_2 , on the circular pattern, and disconnected (not in contact with the pattern). The probe states can be explained by referring to Fig. 3 as follows:

- if the probe is on T_2 : R_2 will have a low value and will give a high V_1 and a low V_2 value
- if the probe contacts the target: R_1 and R_2 are approximately the same, thus giving approximately equal values of V_1 and V_2
- if the probe is on T_1 : R_1 will have a high value and will give a low V_1 and a high V_2 value
- if the probe is not in contact with the disk, V_1 and V_2 will be equal to the supplied voltage (V)

C. Processor unit

An Arduino Nano is used as a processor unit in this experiment. A 5V output (as a power supply) and two analog pins are connected to the T_1 and T_2 probes of the p-type silicon pattern as shown in Fig. 3. The probe for the tool (T_3) is connected to a ground pin. The changes in analog voltage at T_1 and T_2 are received via serial port and stored as a .txt file. The data is then cleaned and processed using Python version 3.8.8 in Jupyter Notebook 6.3.0, and Microsoft® Excel® for Microsoft 365. A light-emitting diode (LED) and a sound indicator are implemented in the processing unit. The LED is used to indicate to the experimenter which probe state the participant is currently on (but not visible to the participant during the experiment). The sound indicator will inform the participant that the task was successfully completed to let them know to stop and proceed to the next task.

D. Laryngoscope setup

The laryngoscope mock-up is 3D-printed with an Objet30 Prime, and Prusa SL1 printer using PETG resin (Fig. 2). The tubing part is printed to have the same dimensions as the laryngoscope used in the operating room, namely of the STEINER operating laryngoscope, 8661 CN, Karl Storz, with the inner proximal diameter of 24.5 mm x 14.5 mm ellipse, the inner distal diameter of 15.5 mm x 13.5 mm ellipse, and the length of 18 cm. The distal end of the laryngoscope is connected to a casing that holds the pattern and connects it to the processing unit. The pattern is slotted vertically

and is connected to a spring-loaded conductive pin where different patterns are interchangeable. The part where the photolithography pattern is located represents the task at the level of the patient's vocal cords.

E. Stableyeser robot-assisted system

The Stableyeser (Fig. 4) is a robot-assisted system developed at the Robot-assisted Surgery Group, KU Leuven, to perform retinal vein cannulation in vitreoretinal surgery [23], [24]. The assistive functionality of the robot is to reduce the hand tremor tenfold and lock and immobilize the tool at will. In addition, the robot has a fixed remote center of motion (RCM) where the tool's tangential motion is eliminated at the RCM. This helps stabilize the retina when manipulating the instrument. In transoral laser vocal fold surgery, the surgeon controls the laser with one hand and controls a tool with the other hand to grasp, hold, and manipulate the larynx tissue. TLM has similar requirements as vitreoretinal surgery, which is to reach the tissue precisely while avoiding collision with the anatomy. In principle, after properly grasped, the tool could be locked in place so that the laser can precisely dissect the tissue. Note that in conventional TLM operation, there is currently no way to lock the tools. It is anticipated that the damping and RCM fixation offered by the Stableyeser can be adapted and used in TLM. The Stableyeser's design requirement is to perform vitreoretinal surgery at $10\ \mu\text{m}$ target with its 25 mm-long tool [23]. However, in TLM, the tool length is approximately 180 mm. The understanding of how this longer length affects the robot's performance in TLM can help future adaptations to fully optimize the Stableyeser to work in the TLM environment. In this study, the tool holder section of the Stableyeser is adapted to hold TLM tools as shown in Fig. 5. The microscope position is located at the back similar to the free-hand experiment setup.

III. ORGANISATION OF EXPERIMENT

A study was approved by the Ethics Committee of UZ Leuven (S65808) for a randomized experiment with adaptive sample size. The study is conducted over one year starting from November 2022. The study includes 32 volunteer participants, including 18 clinical staff of the University Hospital Leuven, Belgium (3 surgeons, 3 residents, and 12 nurses), and 14 engineers from KU Leuven, Belgium. Out of 32 participants, 31 participated in the free-hand tool positioning experiment, 5 participated in the experiment with the co-manipulation robot (four of which also participated in the free-hand experiment). The experiment was performed in the operating room of the University Hospital Leuven (UZ Leuven) to maximally simulate the environment of laryngeal transoral surgery.

The experiment setup is shown in Fig. 1. The mock-up laryngoscope containing the target patterns is mounted to an elevated stand in the same position as it would take on in TLM. The participant visualizes these targets through the binoculars of the surgical microscope located behind them. The microscope is set to the maximum magnification (7.8x) with a 400 mm working distance. Each participant can adjust their

Fig. 4: Stableyeser robot-assisted system: setup used in vitreoretinal surgery

Fig. 5: Adaptation of the Stableyeser robot-assisted system to be used for the tool positioning experiment in this study

surgical chair to a comfortable position. While performing the experiment, the surgical microscope records a video of how the tools move at the targeted pattern. The video is used as a second authenticator to verify the correctness of the data when performing data cleaning and data processing. For participants that participated in both experiments, the experiment is divided into two parts: Free-hand tool manipulation – to determine the human limitation in TLM, and Robot-assisted tool manipulation – to give an example of how the robot improves the performance in TLM. Participants who participated in both experiments performed the free-hand experiment first and left for approximately one month before performing the robot-assisted experiment. This is to minimize the effect of prior

Fig. 6: Experimental setup and procedure to pinpoint a probe onto each pattern. Fig. 6A, 6B, and 6D represent the experimental procedure. Fig. 6C emphasizes the pattern attached to the orange disk located behind the yellow laryngoscope.

experience from one experiment impacting the result of the other.

A. Experiment 1: Free-hand tool manipulation

The participant holds the probe with their dominant hand. Participants were not allowed to use the other hand e.g. to assist and stabilize the instrument but were allowed to rest the dominant hand on the chair which is also possible in clinical practice. The participant was then asked to position the probe at the proximal tip of the laryngoscope (red circle in Fig. 6A). After a start signal, the participant moves the probe inside the laryngoscope, indicated in Fig. 6B, and tries to touch the indicated pattern (for example, pattern 1, the largest circle in Fig. 6C). The positioning task is considered successful if the participant is able to maintain uninterrupted contact for two seconds. If the position is held shorter, it will be marked as a “fluke attempt”. This approach is also used in the study of Gijbels *et al.* [15]. Only after two seconds of correct contact, a beeping sound will be generated, marking a successful attempt. The participant can then move the probe back to the initial position (Fig. 6D) and wait to start the next pattern. The experiment is completed once all seven patterns are performed. The participant can choose to stop the experiment if judged to be unable to complete the task (e.g. when considering the targets too difficult to reach). To avoid the participant’s performance learning curve affecting the result, the number of trials is kept at a minimum while still ensuring that each participant has a good understanding of the experiment. Before the actual experiment starts, participants are asked to perform a test run where they go through all the patterns once without any data being recorded. At this stage, participants are allowed to ask questions and to be accustomed to the environment. Then, the experiment is conducted with

a single trial for each pattern. The duration for each entire experiment is approximately 40 minutes.

B. Experiment 2: Robot-assisted tool manipulation

The same stainless steel probe is now attached to the Stableyeser robot via a connector as shown in Fig. 4. The tool is pre-inserted into the laryngoscope, leaving approximately 2 mm depth distance before the probe contacts the pattern. The probe is initially placed at the right with approximately equidistance from all the circular patterns. Then, similar to Experiment 1, after a start signal, the participant is asked to move the tool to the specified target (but now by using the handle of the robot). The same data is recorded and a similar processing is done after the experiment.

C. Post-processing of data

The results from both experiments are first analyzed individually and then compared with each other. For both experiments, the data gathered from the processor unit and the video recordings from the surgical microscope are processed to compute:

- 1) total time taken to finish the task per pattern
- 2) total time (and the number of times) the probe disengages from the pattern (indicated as “No Contact” in the result graphs section)
- 3) total time (and the number of times) the probe touches the wrong target (indicated as “Wrong Target” in the result graphs section)
- 4) total time (and the number of times) the probe is in contact with the correct pattern but fails to keep the contact for two seconds (indicated as short “On Target” in the result graphs section)

In the case of the robot-assisted experiment, the tool is pre-inserted into the targeted site. This is because the Stableyeser at this stage is not fully adapted for TLM, and has a limitation in the longitudinal translation degrees of freedom. In order to have the same evaluation as the free-hand experiment, the time to navigate the tool from the proximal to the distal end of the laryngoscope (t_{pd}) needs to be subtracted from the free-hand experiment. The time (t_{pd}) is obtained by performing an additional free-hand experiment where participants are asked to move the tools from the proximal tip of the laryngoscope to the distal tip and contact the photolithography pattern. The participant is asked to move at a similar speed and similar manner as if they would do in their free-hand experiment trial. The average t_{pd} is obtained after conducting 25 additional trials to be 2.29 s.

IV. RESULTS

A number of 32 participants contributed to the precision study. In total, 31 participated in the free-hand tool positioning experiment and 5 participated in the robot-assisted experiment (four of which also participated in the free-hand experiment). Figure 7 shows an example of randomly selected individual results from a participant who participated in both the free-hand and robot-assisted tool positioning experiment.

Fig. 7: Example of performance results of one participant on all seven patterns

TABLE I: Result of the free-hand (sample size = 31) and the robot-assisted (sample size = 5) tool positioning experiment: total time taken to complete each task and the number of times the probe contacted the wrong area during each task.

	Free-hand (n = 31)				Robot-assisted (n = 5)			
	Total time (s)		Number of wrong contacts		Total time (s)		Number of wrong contacts	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Pattern 1	14.15	11.08	1.65	2.60	10.53	7.28	0.20	0.45
Pattern 2	13.92	12.30	2.71	4.53	12.94	7.40	0.60	0.89
Pattern 3	20.01	17.95	5.29	8.51	12.49	8.07	0.20	0.45
Pattern 4	23.25	17.10	8.87	10.47	20.32	15.60	0.80	1.10
Pattern 5	31.76	27.85	15.48	17.63	15.24	3.87	2.00	2.55
Pattern 6	51.39	79.60	15.78	37.35	21.20	12.31	3.84	2.95
Pattern 7	78.01	84.32	34.86	51.21	107.10	54.17	18.20	15.45

Table I shows the mean and standard deviation (SD) of the total time taken to complete each task and the number of times the probe incorrectly contacted the wrong area during each task. The mean total time presented in the column of the free-hand experiment in Table I has already been subtracted by $t_{pd} = 2.29$ s which is the average time taken for the probe to move from the starting point to the targeted area. The total time and the number of incorrect contacts from all the participants for each target pattern are presented with a box plot as shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 respectively. The mean performance of free-hand tool positioning capability is compared with the robot-assisted system as shown in Fig. 10.

V. DISCUSSION

In this section, the performance trend and precision limitations from the free-hand and the robot-assisted experiments results are analyzed and discussed. Due to the imbalance in sample size between the two approaches, this study aims to only observe the result and does not provide a statistical comparison between the two approaches.

From the individual results of Fig. 7, participants spent more time completing the task when the difficulty level increased

(smaller target size). It was confirmed that there exists a significant impact of hand tremors during free-hand experiments which makes aiming at the target site inside the laryngoscope more difficult. It is understood that this impacted the number of wrong target contacts and increased the number of disengaged contacts. This is reflected in Fig. 7 in smaller targets such as pattern 5 to 7. The free-hand performance observed in pattern 5 to 7 severely fluctuates between “Wrong target” and “No contact”.

Referring to Fig. 8, the same trend can be seen when analyzing the data of the free-hand experiment containing all participants. Participants take more time to complete each task as the difficulty level increases. At Pattern 4 with a diameter of 0.8 mm, the SD jumped strongly compared to Pattern 3 with a diameter of 1.0 mm. This suggests that the task is too difficult to reliably execute, and thus more random performance occurs between each participant. This effect amplifies when the target size becomes smaller, for example, Pattern 7: 0.1 mm has the highest SD and extreme outliers. From this information, humans can reach a targeted area of size 1.0 mm or larger while maintaining respectable timing. However, the number of incorrect contacts should also be taken into account when

analyzing the results.

In the surgical environment, it would be ideal to correctly reach the desired target the first time the tool is inserted inside the laryngoscope. Touching, grasping, (or ablating in case of using the laser system) the wrong target several times risks damaging the larynx tissue. Thus, the optimal performance is not only to execute fast but also to minimize contacting the wrong target. Figure 9 plots the number of times the participant touches the wrong target during free-hand and robot-assisted tool positioning. This plot counts the number of times the probe came into contact with any other area that is not the circular target. For the free-hand experiment, at pattern 2 with target size of 1.5 mm, the average number of wrong contacts is already 2.7 times. This gets drastically worse for the next target size of 1.0 mm (pattern 3) as it is shown to have 5.3 average wrong contacts. While humans can finish the task at a respectable time down to the target size of 1.0 mm, if the criteria of not touching the wrong target are included, the cutoff line for reliable human free-hand tool positioning would be 1.5 mm.

In the robot-assisted experiment, the impact of participants' prior experience from the free-hand experiment is minimized as both experiments were conducted on different dates, approximately one month apart. When introducing the robot-assisted system, the total execution time is only slightly reduced. As observed during the experiment and from the video recordings, participants need time to "aim" their probe before touching the target area. However, the problem of contacting the wrong target area is greatly reduced. The performance variation between each participant is reduced with the help of a robot-assisted system. When analyzing the limitation of the robot-assisted system, a drop in performance could be observed after moving from pattern 6 to pattern 7 based on Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. Table I shows that all robot-assisted tasks outperformed the free-hand experiment except the execution time of the smallest pattern which took 107.10 s. It was found that one participant spent much more time than the other four, impacting the mean duration of the entire population. This aspect is considered an artifact of the low sample size. More experiments and participants would be needed to make firm conclusions on the 0.1 mm target. Based on this experiment, one can conclude that the Stableyeser robot can operate precisely down to a 0.2 mm diameter circular region, or in other words, its operation limit is within a 0.2 mm diameter region. Note also that the Stableyeser has been employed successfully to cannulated retinal vessels with diameters below 0.1 mm [15]. Compared to the retina which the target is approximately 25 mm away from the RCM, this distance is much larger (180 mm) in vocal fold surgery.

Figure 10 shows the comparison between the mean execution time and the number of wrong contacts between free-hand and robot-assisted tool positioning. One clear observation when comparing the free-hand motion with the robot-assisted system is that the robot-assisted system can effectively reduce the number of times the probe contacts the wrong target. This effect can be observed in Fig. 10 and is also confirmed by the video recordings of the participant's performance. In the free-hand trial, when the task gets more difficult, the participant

Fig. 8: Box plot of the total execution time to successfully reach each targeted pattern in the experiment: comparison between free-hand tool positioning experiment and experiment with the Stableyeser robot-assisted system

Fig. 9: Box plot of the number of incorrect contacts during each experiment for each pattern: comparison between free-hand tool positioning experiment and experiment with the Stableyeser robot-assisted system

tends to randomly touch the target area in a "trial and error" manner rather than having a concrete aim at the target before touching it. The damping action of the robot provides great assistance to the participant, allowing them to aim better at the target before contacting it with the probe.

VI. CONCLUSION

Several robot-assisted systems have been developed for TLM and a better understanding of tool positioning precision could set firm design requirements and optimization. Currently, there is limited work to analyze the human tool positioning performance in vocal fold TLM. This study conducts an experiment to determine the human baseline for tool positioning capability in a simulated vocal fold TLM environment. The result is used as a general clinical baseline

for human performance and forms a key design requirement of a soon-to-be-developed robot-assisted system. The experimental setup can be used to validate the performance of a novel robot-assisted system. The experiment setup proved a successful attempt to record a baseline for human tool positioning precision and is also successful at validating a novel robot-assisted system.

In TLM, hand tremor plays an important part as the surgeon needs to navigate the tools inside a long cylindrical-shape laryngoscope. During tissue manipulation, failing to reach the correct target means the forceps or grasper needs to re-grab the tissue. Failing multiple times prolongs surgical time and risks damaging the tissue. Free-hand experiment confirms this behavior as when the pattern is smaller than 1.5 mm, the number of incorrect contacts rises significantly. Thus, an acceptable robot-assisted system not only needs to perform a targeting task promptly but should not contact the undesired target. The Stableyesser that has a parallelogram motion damping and a fixed RCM helps eliminate the incorrect contact problem significantly and even has a faster timing to complete the task. The Stableyesser system can perform precisely down to a target area of 0.2 mm diameter, proving the capability to assist TLM at this early stage where only minimum adaptation is made for it to be used with TLM. Further adaptation is foreseen to make the Stableyesser fully compatible with TLM and to be used in clinical operating room setup, together with additional experiments to analyze its performance.

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Fig. 10: Comparison between free-hand and robot-assisted tool positioning experiment: Top - total time taken to complete each pattern, bottom - number of times the probe contacted the wrong area

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